

Values Re-Orientation and Students' National Development among Public Senior Secondary Schools Students in Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

This paper examined values re-orientation and students' national development among public senior secondary schools students in Rivers State. The factors under investigations are the extent Art Education and Science Education enhance students' national development in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The study made use of correlational research design. The population of the consists 13,400 SSIII students in Obio/Akpor local government area of Rivers State. The sample size of the study is 400 SSIII students. Simple random sampling technique was used which gives equal opportunity to all the population. The researcher made use of self-structured questionnaire to gather data from the respondents. The instrument was validated using experts in guidance and counseling and measurement and evaluation. The researcher used test-retest method to achieve the reliability of the instrument which Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to obtain a reliability coefficient of 0.86. The data collected were analysed using mean and standard deviation for the research questions while the null hypotheses were tested using z-test statistical tool at 0.05 level of significant. Based on the analysis, the findings of the study revealed that Art Education and Science Education have enhance students' national development in public secondary schools in Rivers State. Therefore, the study recommends that: Federal Government should develop a strong Art Education and Science curriculum so as to provide the opportunity for students to solve real-world problems through creativity and to convey their talents to others and government should make the teaching of religious and moral education a compulsory course in secondary schools.

Key Words: Art, Science, Education, Values Re-Orientation, Students, National Development, Values

INTRODUCTION

The growth and development of a nation do not depend solely on the material and scientific achievements it recorded. Partly, it lies on the moral qualities of the individuals charged with the responsibility of national development. It lies on their understanding of the values and the level of the moral consciousness of the society in question. Kanu (2015) defined values as the quality of being distinctively useful and desirable. Nigeria's image as the giant of Africa has suffered some setbacks as a result of anti-social and criminal acts, with a high rate of corruption. The decline and fall of Nigerians in behavior has reached unacceptable level. It is regrettable that the educational system has deteriorated to the extent that instead of being an agent of transformation, empowerment and an instrument of clearing the minds of the young ones to become useful members of the society, has today become an agency of imparting negative values in the minds of the young ones.

Lack of value orientation in Nigeria educational system manifests itself in all levels of education, (primary, secondary and tertiary institutions). As teachers, we have seen different forms of corruption existing in our institutions of today (Osisioma, 2022). For example, examination malpractice, financial malpractice between students and lecturers, embezzlement, exploitation of students, lecturers taking advantage of students, etc. The existence of different forms of corruption in many Nigerian institutions has led to the decay of positive moral values in schools. Corruption and lack of value orientation in the society have enormity of negative effects on the output of graduate in the area of productivity and the degree of acceptance in the society.

Many programmes have been adopted by various governments in Nigeria to stop the menace of lack of value orientation, but they proved inadequate. In recognition to the provisions of the objectives on NPE, this paper views that, Art and Science Education has a unique role to play, looking at the creative nature of the subject to stop these vices in the society. Art and Science Education has a great impact on national development. It displays the most sophisticated forms of visual experience, skill acquisition and information dissemination towards social transformation of an individual. Art Education is important in learning and teaching and can be used as a tool in the present value reorientation processes in Nigeria. Osagie (2016) reflects on President Buhari's slogan, "let the change begin with me" on mass media. This is possible because messages can be translated in practical form where those without any form of formal education can also benefit. Effective communication helps a great deal in national development. The value reorientation process is a high-priority of the present government of Nigeria. Citizens must therefore unite to ensure its success. It is against this background that the study examines values re-orientation and students' national development among public senior secondary schools students in Rivers State.

Concept of Value Orientation

When one talk of value reorientation, it means the principles of right or wrong that are accepted by individual or social groups (Word Net, 2012). Value orientation can also be seen as high moral intelligence and entrenchment of strong values for the development and prosperity of the Nigerian society. It is a transformation on a fundamental shift in the deep orientation of a person, an organization, or a society such that the world is seen in new ways, new actions and results which become possible that were impossible prior to the transformation (Asobie, 2022). It also means the change of the moral character for better through the renewal of the innermost nature.

Reorientation is the act of changing, adjusting, aligning or realigning something in a new or different reaction. Value reorientation is therefore conceptualized as the act “of deliberately attempting to change the direction which attitudes and beliefs in Nigeria are currently orientated or the act of adjusting or aligning behavior, attitudes and beliefs of Nigerians in a new or different direction within the public discourse of contemporary Nigerian politics”.

Njoku (2021) sees value reorientation as inculcating good values that can help Nigeria out of her numerous predicaments and can refocus the nation through greatness. A closer look at the above definition, would make one agree that Nigeria would be rapidly transformed if she embraces good moral values, which have the potentials to re-orientate the attitude and behaviours of Nigerians and to bring significant reduction in corruption, indiscipline, immorality, terrorism, kidnapping and other social vices. This paper believes that value orientation in Nigeria can only be attained through the effective use of the power of creativity in Art and Science Education to reform the schools and to an extent the society in order to achieve meaningful development. What this means is that, if students are instilled with good values at the early stages of their lives, they will grow and cherish them.

Why the Need for Value Reorientation in Nigeria

In Africa, the larger a country, the larger the problems in terms of governance. One of the difficult things to effect in Nigeria today is restoration of our national values and integrity especially when a negative attitude has been formed by past governments. conveniently argued that only a good educational approach can transform a society by reorienting the values. This paper believes that the best approach is the adoption of Art and Science Education for gradual and sustainable value change towards national development. Art Education and its activities have unique roles to play (Osioma, 2022). Art like wind is everywhere and if well utilized, can sustain and improve an already collapsed nation like Nigeria. The idea of getting rich quick and by whatever means has not helped matters.

Concept of National Development

The concept of national development is all encompassing. It entails industrialization, human capital development and social as well as educational quality of the people. All nations of the world attain such height only by tapping the tremendous power of education in their pursuit for the attainment of national objectives. For example, the Germans during the second Reich of 1871 used education as an instrument par excellence for the unification of all the Germans, while Japanese during the Meiji Restoration used education to inculcate and propagate such cardinal virtues as benevolence, fidelity, justice and integrity in the life of the people (Kanu, 2015). In all these cases, each country demonstrated unflinching commitment to the realization of national imperatives. When the Meiji period ended, with the death of the emperor in 1912, Japan had a highly educated population free of feudal class restrictions.

The United Nations Human Development Report (UNHDR, 2005) pronounced a grim verdict on Nigerian developmental statues. The report says alleges that “while people are living long throughout the world, the reverse is the case in Nigeria”. UNHDR (2005) specifies that life expectancy in Nigeria has fallen from 51:6 to 43:4 years, rating our developmental table from 151st position it occupied in 2004 to 158th position out of the total of 177 countries covered in the assessment. Umoru (2015) notes a front-page report title "World Bank rates Nigeria second poorest nation". The report further “cites Nigeria as a resource dependent nation, which could have produced capital five times higher than it did in 2000, if only it had made a moderate effort to save”.

Influence of Art Education on Value Reorientation

Art Education has its roots in drawing, which, with reading, writing, singing, and playing instruments comprise the basic elementary school curriculum in the seventeenth century (Mamza, 2017). Drawing has continued to be the basic component of the core curriculum throughout the eighteenth and nineteenth centuries, when educators saw drawing as important in teaching handwork, nature study, Geography, and other subjects. Art education later expanded to include painting, design, graphicart, and the ‘plastic arts’ (e.g. sculpture and ceramics) although art has continued to be seen primarily as utilitarian. This is the view of 1993 Arts Education Partnership Working Group study. The group study believes that art improves multicultural understanding and the development of higher–order thinking skills, creativity, and problem–solving abilities.

Benefits of Art Education for National Development

1. Art Education stimulates and develops imagination, critical thinking, refines cognitive and creative skills.

2. It has a tremendous impact on the developmental growth of every child and has proven to help level the "learning field" across socio-economic boundaries.
3. Strengthens problem-solving and critical-thinking skills, adding to overall academic achievement and school success.
4. Develops a sense of craftsmanship, quality task performance, and goal-setting— skills needed to succeed in the classroom and beyond.
5. Teaches children life skills such as developing an informed perception, articulating a vision, learning to solve problems and making decisions, building self-confidence and self-discipline, developing the ability to imagine what might be, and accepting responsibility to complete tasks from start to finish, nurtures important values, including team-building skills; respecting alternative viewpoints; and appreciating and being aware of different cultures and traditions.

Need for Value Re-orientation through Scientific Attitude and Scientific Method

The major contributions of science education are imbedded in the inculcation of scientific attitude among its learners through its study. The credit of development of scientific attitudes however, goes to the scientific methods adopted by sciences both in its development and application. A subject can be named as science provided it encompasses the two essential features as scientific attitude and scientific method. Both aspects are given important place in the curriculum of the teaching of sciences at any stage of teacher preparation (Osagie, 2016).

Science education thus can play a vital role in checking and solving these problems through development of knowledge, understanding, skills, abilities and attitudes of the citizens of a country. The study of science has its special importance both in the personal and social life of an individual. The value of science education in the development of scientific attitudes which are transferable strives to remove the superstitions, false beliefs, wrong notions spread in the society and cultivate the habits of proper reasoning, observation and experimentation, leading to a firm belief in testing and verification of facts. It creates a spirit of curiosity for knowing about new things, discovering their environment and penetrating deeply into the nature of things and events surrounding them.

One of the major and essential aims of science education is the development of scientific attitude among its learners. Thus, it is imperative for science teachers and educators to understand the meaning, significance and process of the development of such attitude. It can be defined as open mindedness, a desire for accurate knowledge, confidence in procedure for seeking knowledge and the expectation that the solution of the problem will come through the use of verified knowledge. Through science education, the student can develop scientific attitudes characterized by open-mindedness, curiosity, tolerance, honest doubt, respect for another's point of view,

critical observation and thought, freedom from superstitions, judgement made on scientific facts, faith in cause and effect relationship and a planned procedure in solving problems (Joshi, 2015).

Need for Values Education in Nigerian Secondary Schools

There is an urgent need for values education in Nigerian secondary schools to help our child develop proper moral character to assist them make proper ethical choices for sustainable and meaningful living. There is obvious erosion of values in our society, of growing up of children and youth in the age of instant gratification, cultism, commercialization of education, negative impact of media, sexual immorality, distortion of values and so on. The school system needs to come up with ways of infusing morality and values into students. Modal (2017) provides the following as being the objectives of values education:

- a. To improve the integral growth of human beings.
- b. To create attitudes and improvement towards sustainable lifestyle.
- c. To increase awareness about our national history our cultural heritage, constitutional rights, national integration, community development and environment.
- d. To create and develop awareness about the values and their significance and role.
- e. To know about various living and non-living organisms and their interaction with environment.

Gulati and Pant, (2016) in treating the subject of values education takes it from the angle of the individual and that of the society. From individual's perspective, the source sees the purpose of values education as effort aimed at enabling students achieve personal fulfillment for success in life and work through inculcation of appropriate values. From the societal perspectives, values education aims to prepare young people to contribute to the society/nation and world around as responsible members of society. The source further added that education for values aims at promoting broader capabilities, attitudes and skills in students, that matter not just in schools but also in life beyond schools, making the world a better place not just for themselves but also for their family, friends, colleagues and others. Education for values, in the view of this source, underpins the understanding that values are to be inculcated in students, not just for their own interest, but also for the common good reflecting the balance between individual's interest and larger interest.

Commonwealth of Australia (2005) noted that values based education can strengthen students' self-esteem, optimism and commitment to personal fulfillment; and help students exercise ethical

judgment and social responsibility; it also helps students understand and develop personal and social responsibilities. The benefits of effective values education in line with the above source is paraphrased below as:

1. Helping students understand and be able to apply values such as care and compassion; honesty and trustworthiness; integrity; respect; responsibility and understanding, tolerance and inclusion
2. Promotion of Nigerian democratic way of life and values and respecting the diversity in Nigerian schools
3. Articulating the values of the school community and applying these consistently in the practices of the school.
4. Promoting partnership with students, staff, families and the school community as part of a whole-school approach to educating students, enabling them to exercise responsibility and strengthening their resilience;
5. Enhances safe and supportive learning environment in which students are encouraged to explore their own, their schools and their communities' values;
6. Leads to emergence of trained and resourceful teachers able to use a variety of different models, modes and strategies in teaching;
7. It will lead to emergence of a curriculum that meets the individual needs of students; and are regularly reviewed to ensure that they meet the intended outcomes.

Statement of the Problem

Social vices have reached an alarming rate. This is observed to be caused by high rate of moral decadence among the students and youths. There seems to be different forms of unethical dispositions that have led to total collapse of societal values. The values of honesty, hard work, dedication, respect for elders, respect for human dignity, decent dressing, humility, studious and discipline among others seem to be gradually diminishing in our society and most importantly among the students and youths. Lack of respect, dishonesty, laziness, pride, indecent dressing, lack of discipline among others have taken over. These seem to be the root causes of different sorts of misdemeanor that make students and youths get involved in negative activities such as political thuggery, crisis, violence, get rich syndrome, armed robbery, rape, prostitution etc. It was on this background that this study was carried out to examine values re-orientation and

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students' national development among public senior secondary schools students in Rivers State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to determine the values re-orientation and students' national development among public senior secondary schools students in Rivers State. Specifically, the objectives of the study are to:

- 1 examine the extent Art Education as a channel for value re-orientation enhance students' national development among public senior secondary schools students in Rivers State
- 2 determine the extent Science Education as a channel for value re-orientation enhance students' national development among public senior secondary schools students in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised for the study:

- 1 To what extent does Art Education as a channel for value re-orientation enhance students' national development among public senior secondary schools students in Rivers State?
- 2 To what extent does Science Education as a channel for value re-orientation enhance students' national development among public senior secondary schools students in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The researchers formulated the following hypotheses that guided the study

- 1 There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of the male and female students on the extent Art Education as a channel for value re-orientation enhance students' national development among public senior secondary schools students in Rivers State
- 2 There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of the male and female students on the extent Science Education as a channel for value re-orientation enhance students' national development among public senior secondary schools students in Rivers State

METHODOLOGY

The study made use of correlational research design. The population of the consists 13,400 SSIII students in Obio/Akpor local government area of Rivers State. The sample size of the study is 400 SSIII students. Simple random sampling technique was used which gives equal opportunity to all the population. The researcher made use of self structured questionnaire titled "Value Re-orientation and Students National Development Questionnaire (VRSNDQ) to gather data from the respondents. The instrument was validated using experts in guidance and counseling and measurement and evaluation. The researcher used test-retest method to achieve the reliability of the instrument which Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to obtain a reliability

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coefficient of 0.86. The data collected were analysed using mean and standard deviation for the research questions while the null hypotheses were tested using z-test statistical tool at 0.05 level of significant.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: To what extent does Art Education as a channel for value re-orientation enhance students’ national development among public senior secondary schools students in Rivers State?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation analysis on the extent Art Education as a channel for value re-orientation enhance students’ national development among public senior secondary schools students in Rivers State.

S/ No	Questionnaire Items	Male Students =170			Female Students = 230		
		Mean \bar{x}	SD	Remarks	Mean \bar{x}	SD	Remarks
1.	Art education stimulates and develops imagination and critical thinking which enhance national development.	2.89	0.85	High Extent	2.95	0.86	High Extent
2.	Art education has tremendous impact on the developmental growth of every child which helps in learning field and national education.	2.86	0.83	High Extent	2.86	0.84	High Extent
3.	Art education strengthens problem solving and critical thinking skills that enhance national development.	2.78	0.83	High Extent	2.91	0.85	High Extent
4.	Art education helps students in building self-confidence and self – discipline which enhance national development.	2.83	0.84	High Extent	2.82	0.84	High Extent
5.	Art education helps students in team building skills which enhance national development.	2.86	0.84	High Extent	2.86	0.84	High Extent
Grand Total		2.84	0.84		2.88	0.85	

Source: Field Survey, 2024

The analysis in Table 1 above revealed that the respondents agreed on the view that Art education stimulates and develops imagination and critical thinking which enhance national development. The analysis still indicated that the respondents accepted on the point that art education has tremendous impact on the developmental growth of every child which helps in

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learning field and national education. It was also observed in the study that the respondents accepted the fact that art education strengthens problem solving and critical thinking skills that enhance national development. The analysis still showed that the respondents agreed on the view that art education helps students in building self-confidence and self – discipline which enhance national development. The analysis also revealed that the respondents agreed on the view that art education helps students in team building skills which enhance national development.

Research Question 2: To what extent does Science Education as a channel for value re-orientation enhance students’ national development among public senior secondary schools students in Rivers State?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation analysis on the extent Science Education as a channel for value re-orientation enhance students’ national development among public senior secondary schools students in Rivers State.

S/ No	Questionnaire Items	Male Students =170			Female Students = 230		
		Mean \bar{x}	SD	Remarks	Mean \bar{x}	SD	Remarks
6.	Science education plays a vital role in checking and solving problem through development of knowledge.	2.86	0.84	High Extent	2.91	0.85	High Extent
7.	Science education helps in development of scientific attitude among learners which enhance national development.	2.83	0.84	High Extent	2.95	0.86	High Extent
8.	Science education improve the integral growth of human begins.	2.97	0.86	High Extent	2.98	0.86	High Extent
9.	Science education increase awareness about our right, national integration.	2.94	0.86	High Extent	2.99	0.86	High Extent
10.	Science education helps the students to know how to interact with their environments.	2.92	0.85	High Extent	3.00	0.87	High Extent
Grand Total		2.90	0.85		2.97	0.86	

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

The data analysis in Table 2 above indicated that the respondents accepted the point that Science education plays a vital role in checking and solving problem through development of knowledge. The analysis also showed that the respondents agreed on the view that science education helps in development of scientific attitude among learners which enhance national development. It was still noticed in the analysis that the respondents agreed on the fact that science education improve the integral growth of human begins. The analysis also revealed that the respondents accepted the view that science education increase awareness about our right, national integration. The study

indicated that the respondents agreed on the fact that science education helps the students to know how to interact with their environments.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of the male and female students on the extent Art Education as a channel for value re-orientation enhance students' national development among public senior secondary schools students in Rivers State.

Table 3: Z-test Analysis of significant difference in the mean ratings of the male and female students on the extent Art Education as a channel for value re-orientation enhance students' national development among public senior secondary schools students in Rivers State.

Status	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	df	z-cal	z-crit	Decision
		\bar{X}					
Male Students	170	2.84	0.84				
				398	2.29	1.96	Accepted
Female Students	230	2.88	0.85				

The analysis on Table 3 revealed that the z-cal of 1.29 is less than the z-crit of 1.96. Therefore, the calculated z-ratio is statistically significant at a 0.05 level of significance since it is smaller than the given critical value of z-ratio. So, the hypothesis 1 is thus accepted and the conclusion is that there is no significant difference on the mean ratings of the respondents on the extent equal opportunity to students enhance the educational development of the less privilege students in Rivers State.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of the male and female students on the extent Science Education as a channel for value re-orientation enhance students' national development among public senior secondary schools students in Rivers State.

Table 4: Z-test Analysis of significant difference in the mean ratings of the male and female students on the extent Science Education as a channel for value re-orientation enhance students’ national development among public senior secondary schools students in Rivers State

Status	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Df	z-cal	z-crit	Decision
		\bar{X}					
Male Students	170	2.90	0.85	398	1.24	1.96	Accepted
Female Students	230	2.97	0.86				

The analysis on Table 4 indicated that the z-cal of 1.24 is smaller than the z-crit of 1.96. Therefore, the calculated z-ratio is statistically significant at a 0.05 level of significance since it is less than the given critical value of z-ratio. Therefore, the hypothesis 2 is thus accepted and the conclusion is that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of the male and female students on the extent Science Education as a channel for value re-orientation enhance students’ national development among public senior secondary schools students in Rivers State.

Discussion of Findings

The findings in research question one: To what extent does Art Education as a channel for value re-orientation enhance students’ national development among public senior secondary schools students in Rivers State revealed that Art Education as a channel for value re-orientation enhance students’ national development among public senior secondary schools students in Rivers State. The corresponding hypothesis 1 was accepted and concluded that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of the male and female students on the extent Art Education as a channel for value re-orientation enhance students’ national development among public senior secondary schools students in Rivers State. This finding is in collaboration with Daramola (2014), who observed that Art education stimulates and develops imagination and critical thinking which enhance national development. The analysis still indicated that the respondents accepted on the point that art education has tremendous impact on the developmental growth of every child which helps in learning field and national education. It was also observed in the study that the respondents accepted the fact that art education strengthens problem solving and critical thinking skills that enhance national development. The analysis still showed that the respondents agreed on the view that art education helps students in building self-confidence and self – discipline which enhance national development. The analysis also revealed that the respondents agreed on the view that art education helps students in team building skills which enhance national development.

The findings in Research Questions two: To what extent does Science Education as a channel for value re-orientation enhance students' national development among public senior secondary schools students in Rivers State indicated that Science Education as a channel for value re-orientation enhance students' national development among public senior secondary schools students in Rivers State. However, the corresponding hypothesis 2 was accepted and concluded that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of the male and female students on the extent Science Education as a channel for value re-orientation enhance students' national development among public senior secondary schools students in Rivers State. This study is in the same view with the Dover (2015), who noted that Science education plays a vital role in checking and solving problem through development of knowledge. The analysis also showed that the respondents agreed on the view that science education helps in development of scientific attitude among learners which enhance national development. It was still noticed in the analysis that the respondents agreed on the fact that science education improve the integral growth of human beings. The analysis also revealed that the respondents accepted the view that science education increase awareness about our right, national integration. The study indicated that the respondents agreed on the fact that science education helps the students to know how to interact with their environments.

Conclusion

This study concludes that Nigerians need values reorientation and Art and Science Education help in the process of values reorientation for national development. There is the need for assisting them at whatever level towards engaging themselves meaningfully. Importantly, there is need to re-orientate the minds of students while teaching for a total turn around. Values reorientation process should be a high priority of the present government of Nigeria. Every students should be part of this exercise for a better tomorrow. On this note, the study also deduced that the desired reorientation that we look for can only be achieved through a vibrant educational programme. That is to say, instead of living the concepts in their theoretical forms alone, practical efforts should be made to employ Art Educators in the implementation of the educational policy documents.

Recommendations

Based on the issued is cussed in this paper, it is therefore recommended that:

- i. The Federal Government should develop a strong Art Education and Science curriculum so as to provide the opportunity for students to solve real-world problems through creativity and to convey their talents to others.
- ii. Government should make the teaching of religious and moral education a compulsory course in secondary schools

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